

1 **Bridgmanite is nearly dry at the top of the lower mantle**

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9

10 **Abstract**

11 Water solubility in the dominant lower-mantle bridgmanite phase remains
12 controversial. Discrepancies between previous results highlight the importance of the
13 growth high-quality single crystals of bridgmanite under high-pressure and
14 high-temperature conditions corresponding to the top of the lower mantle. Here we
15 synthesized high-quality single crystals of aluminous bridgmanite up to 300 μm in
16 size that were saturated with hydrous melt at 24–26 GPa and 1700–1900 K using both
17 stoichiometric and MgO-rich non-stoichiometric hydrous starting materials in a
18 multi-anvil press. Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy measurements on clear and
19 pure spots of the single-crystal bridgmanites did not detect any pronounced
20 OH-stretching bands, which were prominent in some earlier studies. The present
21 results support that the lower-mantle dominated bridgmanite is nearly dry, at least at
22 the top of the lower mantle, and that Al^{3+} and Fe^{3+} cannot enhance water incorporation

23 into the crystal structure even in the presence of oxygen vacancies. Large partition
24 coefficients of water between transition-zone minerals and dry lower-mantle
25 dominated bridgmanite further support dehydration melting at the top of the lower
26 mantle. We suggest that the majority of the top of a pyrolitic lower mantle is nearly
27 dry based on the dry principal minerals and stability of hydrous phases in this region.

28 **Key words:** Water solubility, single crystal, bridgmanite, dry, lower mantle

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45 1. Introduction

46 Water is the dominant constituent of volatiles in Earth's interior and plays an
47 important role in its evolution and dynamics (e.g., Hirschmann, 2006; Keppler and
48 Bolfan-Casanova, 2006). It is widely accepted that the upper mantle's water storage
49 capacity is relatively small, but that of the mantle transition zone is large because of
50 the increasing water solubility in major minerals with depth (e.g., Bolfan-Casanova et
51 al., 2000; Ohtani et al., 2004, 2015; Hirschmann, 2006; Pearson et al., 2014; Fei et al.,
52 2017, 2020a). However, the question of how much water is stored in the lower mantle
53 remains debated owing to large discrepancies between previous results of the water
54 solubility in bridgmanite, the most abundant mineral in this region (Meade et al., 1994;
55 Bolfan-Casanova et al., 2000, 2003; Litasov et al., 2003; Murakami et al., 2002; Inoue
56 et al., 2010; Panero et al., 2015). Constraints on the water solubility in bridgmanite
57 are therefore crucial to understand the water storage capacity of the lower mantle and
58 its relevance for dehydration melting, seismic anomalies, and dynamics of Earth's
59 interior.

60 An infrared spectroscopy (IR) study by Meade et al. (1994) showed that MgSiO_3
61 bridgmanite can contain ~ 60 ppm wt. H_2O at 27 GPa and 2100 K based on the
62 presence of OH-stretching absorbance bands at 3423 and 3480 cm^{-1} . Later studies
63 further suggested that aluminous bridgmanite synthesized at 24–26 GPa and 1700–
64 2000 K can contain 0.1–0.2 wt.% H_2O based on the strong and broad OH-stretching
65 bands detected at frequencies of ~ 3200 – 3300 , 3400 – 3460 , and 3600 – 3690
66 cm^{-1} (Murakami et al., 2002; Litasov et al., 2003), which is significantly higher than

67 that determined for pure MgSiO₃ bridgmanite based on Fourier-transform infrared
68 spectroscopy (FTIR) and secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS) measurements
69 (Meade et al., 1994; Litasov et al., 2003; Inoue et al., 2010). The reported dissolution
70 of such large amounts of water in these aluminous bridgmanites (Murakami et al.,
71 2002; Litasov et al., 2003) depends on the integration of the IR absorption bands in
72 the FTIR measurements (Bolfan-Casanova, 2005). Bolfan-Casanova et al. (2000,
73 2003) demonstrated that the broad and strong IR absorption bands of OH-stretching
74 observed in earlier studies (Meade et al., 1994; Murakami et al., 2002; Litasov et al.,
75 2003) were possibly caused by the presence of inclusions of impurities, such as
76 superhydrous phase B (3350 and 3490 cm⁻¹) and hydrous melt, captured within grains
77 or between grain boundaries. Schmandt et al. (2014) observed intergranular hydrous
78 melt around small bridgmanite grains that exhibited nearly the same broad IR bands at
79 2700–3700 cm⁻¹ as those observed in earlier studies by Murakami et al. (2002) and
80 Litasov et al. (2003). Furthermore, Panero et al. (2015) suggested that bridgmanite
81 synthesized in a laser-heated diamond anvil cell cannot contain above 220 ppm wt.
82 H₂O according to IR measurements. Fu et al. (2019) recently reported that (Al,
83 Fe)-bearing bridgmanite can contain more than 0.1 wt.% H₂O based on both FTIR
84 and SIMS measurements; however, their observed IR absorption bands at ~3230 and
85 ~3460 cm⁻¹ were essentially the same as those presented in Litasov et al. (2003).

86 Bolfan-Casanova (2005) and Fu et al. (2019) both discussed the role of analytical
87 techniques (FTIR and SIMS) and inclusions on these discrepancies and concluded
88 that inclusions of hydrous impurities pose the most serious problem in the debate

89 regarding water solubility in bridgmanite. SIMS cannot distinguish hydrous inclusions
 90 within crystals, although it can be used to measure bulk water contents in small
 91 samples (Bolfan-Casanova, 2005; Fu et al., 2019). Compared with the SIMS
 92 technique, the greatest advantage of FTIR is its ability to relatively easily identify and
 93 distinguish the frequencies of structural OH-stretching absorbance bands from fluid
 94 inclusions and hydrous phases (Bolfan-Casanova, 2005). However, inclusions of
 95 fluids or hydrous phases are difficult to avoid in single crystals of bridgmanite
 96 quenched under high-pressure and high-temperature conditions. The quality of the
 97 bridgmanite crystals in early studies, especially for aluminous bridgmanite, was not
 98 ideal nor were their sizes sufficiently large for FTIR measurements because of the
 99 inevitable inclusions that form in quenching experiments. It is therefore crucial to
 100 synthesize large, high-quality, and inclusion-free single crystals of bridgmanite under
 101 lower-mantle conditions and carefully examine the assignment of the IR absorption
 102 bands.

103 The higher water solubility in aluminous bridgmanite compared with pure
 104 MgSiO₃ bridgmanite reported in earlier studies (Murakami et al., 2002; Litasov et al.,
 105 2003) was originally thought to be caused by the protonation of oxygen vacancies
 106 (OV) that arise from the replacement of silicon by trivalent cations in the bridgmanite
 107 structure according to the following reactions (Navrotsky, 1999) in point defect
 108 notation (Kröger and Vink, 1956):

111 where M represents Al and Fe, subscripts indicate the site, superscripts indicate the
112 charge as (\times) for neutral, ($'$) for negative, and (\cdot) for positive, and $V_O^{\cdot\cdot}$ is an OV that is
113 twice positively charged. However, even in the presence of Al^{3+} and Fe^{3+} cations,
114 OV-bearing bridgmanite does not exhibit strong characteristic OH-bands and has a
115 very low water solubility (below 10 ppm wt. H_2O), which is far from the derived
116 value of 0.55 wt.% H_2O for bridgmanite with 0.9 mol% OV content
117 (Bolfan-Casanova et al., 2003). Although previous studies obtained OV-bearing
118 bridgmanite (Murakami et al., 2002; Litasov et al., 2003; Bolfan-Casanova et al.,
119 2003), the amount of OV was negligible and none obtained single crystals of
120 OV-dominated bridgmanite. Under MgO-saturated conditions, reaction (1) will occur,
121 and thus the formation of OVs in bridgmanite is more favored, which was clarified in
122 our recent studies (Grüninger et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2017, 2019a, 2019b; Fei et al.,
123 2020b). Our recent study also suggested that the amount of OV has a nonlinear
124 dependence on the Al content in bridgmanite (Grüninger et al., 2019; Liu et al.,
125 2019b). It is therefore necessary to create MgO-rich conditions and use specific Al
126 contents in the starting materials to synthesize OV-dominated bridgmanite crystals to
127 examine their water solubility.

128 Here we synthesized large-sized, chemically homogeneous, and inclusion-free
129 single crystals of aluminous bridgmanite at 24–26 GPa and 1700–1900 K from both
130 stoichiometric and MgO-saturated non-stoichiometric compounds in a multi-anvil
131 press. We investigated the phase assemblages, chemical compositions, and
132 single-crystal quality using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray diffraction

133 (XRD), electron microprobe analysis (EPMA), and optical microscopy. We
134 determined the water solubility in single crystals of bridgmanite and coexisting phases
135 (garnet and stishovite) by FTIR. The results show that bridgmanite is nearly dry at the
136 top of Earth's lower mantle. We suggest that the majority of the top of a pyrolitic
137 lower mantle is nearly dry based on the dry major minerals and stability of hydrous
138 phases in this region.

139 **2. Materials and Methods**

140 We prepared two kinds of starting compositions: (i) stoichiometric compounds
141 with chemical compositions of $\text{En}_{90}\text{Cor}_{10}$ (En: MgSiO_3 enstatite; Cor: Al_2O_3 corundum)
142 with 8.8 wt.% H_2O and $\text{En}_{90}\text{FA}_{10}$ (FA: FeAlO_3) with 10 wt.% H_2O and (ii)
143 non-stoichiometric compounds of an $\text{En}_{90}\text{Brm}_{10}$ (Brm, $\text{MgAlO}_{2.5}$ brownmillerite)
144 oxide mixture and glass with 8.8 and 6 wt.% H_2O , respectively. Water is produced by
145 $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$. The oxide mixtures were prepared from reagent-grade MgO , SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 ,
146 $^{57}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, and $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$. Bridgmanite synthesized from the non-stoichiometric
147 compounds is expected to be saturated with periclase in the presence of Al^{3+} and Fe^{3+}
148 to favor the formation of oxygen vacancies, as suggested by reaction (1). Glasses
149 were prepared from oxide mixtures of reagent-grade MgO , SiO_2 , and Al_2O_3 or $^{57}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$,
150 which were fused at a temperature of 2000 K for 1 h, quenched in cold water, and
151 ground into a fine-grained powder. The compositions of the glass starting materials
152 were measured by EPMA in our recent studies (Liu et al., 2019a, 2019b). All starting
153 materials were kept in a vacuum furnace at 400 K for 5–12 h to remove moisture and
154 then put into a $\text{Pt}_{90}\text{Rh}_{10}$ capsule. To avoid Fe loss, we initially put the sample into a

155 small Au-foil capsule, which was then inserted into a Pt₉₀Rh₁₀ capsule prior to
156 welding in runs H4851 and S7158. In run S7119, we also used an Au foil for the
157 sample before insertion into a Pt₉₀Rh₁₀ capsule to simplify welding. All capsules were
158 sealed by arc welding to avoid water loss during the experiment.

159 Synthesis experiments were performed at 24–26 GPa and 1700–1900 K using
160 Cr₂O₃-doped MgO octahedra with 10- and 7-mm edge lengths and a LaCrO₃ sleeve
161 for heating in combination with tungsten carbide cubes with 4- and 3-mm truncated
162 edge lengths in 1200- and 1500-ton multi-anvil apparatuses at the Bayerisches
163 Geoinstitut, University of Bayreuth, Germany (BGI) (Keppler and Frost, 2005; Ishii et
164 al., 2016). To grow large-sized, inclusion-free, and high-quality single crystals, we
165 optimized the growth environment by controlling the heating. We slowly increased
166 the temperature to the target value at high pressure at a rate of 50 °C/min, and then
167 maintained the target temperature for 15–36 h. The samples were quenched to room
168 temperature by shutting off or rapidly decreasing the heating power.

169 The recovered samples were doubly polished to thin sections with thicknesses of
170 70–200 μm for optical microscope observation and Fourier Transform infrared
171 spectroscopy (FTIR) measurements using unpolarized radiation. Textural observations
172 were performed using an LEO1530 scanning electron microscope (SEM) with an
173 acceleration voltage of 15 kV. Chemical analyses of the phases were determined by
174 EMPA using a JEOL JXA-8200 microprobe operating at an acceleration voltage of 15
175 kV and beam current of 5 nA with standards of enstatite for Mg and Si, corundum for
176 Al, and iron metal for Fe. Phases were identified using a micro-focused XRD with a

177 Co anode operated at 40 kV and 500 mA. The XRD profiles of each sample were
178 integrated from two-dimensional diffraction patterns collected for 3 h (Fig. S1 in
179 Supplementary Material). The $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\Sigma\text{Fe}$ ratio of the Fe-bearing sample in run S7158
180 was determined by Mössbauer spectroscopy conducted in transmission mode using a
181 constant acceleration Mössbauer spectrometer with a nominal 50 mCi ^{57}Co point
182 source in a 6-mm Rh matrix (McCammon, 1994).

183 Unpolarized FTIR spectra of the samples with a thickness of $\sim 200\ \mu\text{m}$ in runs
184 IRIS669 and S7119 were measured using a Bruker IFS 120 high-resolution
185 spectrometer at BGI, whereas those of thinner samples in runs IRIS669, IRIS680,
186 S7139, H4851, and S7158 were measured by a Bruker Vertex 80V spectrometer at the
187 State Key Laboratory of Superhard Materials, Jilin University, China. FTIR spectra on
188 clear single-crystal phases were measured using an aperture size of $30\ \mu\text{m}$, whereas
189 those on aggregates of bridgmanite grains and inclusions (e.g., hydrous melt, hydrous
190 phases, or brucite) were measured using an aperture size of $45\text{--}60\ \mu\text{m}$. Two hundred
191 scans were accumulated for each spectrum at a resolution of $2\text{--}4\ \text{cm}^{-1}$. Three to five
192 spectra for each sample were obtained on different regions within both single crystals
193 and aggregates. We evaluated the H_2O solubility in minerals using the calibration
194 method of Paterson (1982), which was adopted in earlier studies for the same minerals
195 (e.g., Bolfan-Casanova et al., 2003; Litasov et al., 2003; Murakami et al., 2002;
196 Panero et al., 2005; Fu et al., 2019). In this case, we can reduce the uncertainties of
197 water analysis from different calibration methods. After subtraction of the IR spectra
198 baseline, the water content is calculated using the equation:

199
$$C_{OH} = \frac{X_i}{150\xi} \int \frac{K(\bar{\nu})}{(3780 - \bar{\nu})}$$

200 where C_{OH} is the concentration of H₂O in ppm wt., X_i is the density factor ($X_i = 10^6 \times$
201 $(18/2d)$, where d is the mineral density) (Bolfan-Casanova et al., 2000), ξ is the
202 orientation factor of 1/3 for the unpolarized spectra of minerals, and $K(\bar{\nu})$ is the
203 absorption coefficient in cm⁻¹ for a given wavenumber ($\bar{\nu}$). Integration was performed
204 over the wavenumber range of 2800–3800 cm⁻¹ according to the quality of the FTIR
205 spectra.

206 **3. Results**

207 **3.1 Single-crystal growth and phase assemblages**

208 The experimental conditions and run products are summarized in Table 1. We
209 obtained high-quality single crystals of bridgmanite up to 300 μm in size saturated
210 with hydrous melt from different starting compositions by using a slow heating rate
211 and longer heating duration under pressure and temperature conditions
212 corresponding to the top of the lower mantle.

213 Fig. 1 shows XRD profiles of the run products, and Fig. 2 exhibits their
214 corresponding back-scattered electron (BSE) images. In run S7119, single crystals of
215 bridgmanite larger than 100 μm in size coexist with garnets of ~200 μm, stishovite of
216 ~100 μm, trace amounts of brucite, and hydrous melt at 24 GPa and 1900 K from the
217 starting material of En₉₀Co_{r10} with 8.8 wt.% H₂O oxide mixture (Figs. 1a, 2a). Upon
218 increasing the pressure to 26 GPa at the same temperature in run S7139, single
219 crystals of bridgmanite up to 300 μm in size coexist with hydrous melt and trace
220 amounts of brucite (Figs. 1b, 2b). For the starting material of En₉₀Br_{m10} with 8.8 wt.%

221 H₂O in run IRIS680, single crystals of bridgmanite coexist with phase D and trace
222 amounts of hydrous melt at 26 GPa and 1700 K (Figs. 1c, 2c). For the starting glass
223 material En₉₀Brm₁₀ with 6 wt.% H₂O in run IRIS669, single crystals of bridgmanite
224 coexisting with hydrous melt and trace amounts of periclase were grown up to 300
225 μm in the middle part of the capsule (Figs. 1d, 2d). In contrast, small grains of
226 bridgmanite (<50 μm) coexist with periclase and trace amounts of brucite in the two
227 capsule ends, i.e., the lower temperature regions, in this run. Moreover, we
228 synthesized single crystals of (Fe, Al)-bearing bridgmanite larger than 100 μm
229 saturated with ferropericlase and hydrous melt at 26 GPa and 1900 K from En₉₀FA₁₀
230 with 10 wt.% H₂O oxide mixture and glass in runs H4851 and S7158, respectively
231 (Figs. 1e, 1f, 2e, 2f).

232 We examined the quality of the single crystals using optical microscopy in
233 transmitted light (Fig. S2) in addition to BSE observations under high magnification
234 (Fig. S3). The single crystals of aluminous bridgmanite appear pure and clean in runs
235 S7119, S7139, IRIS669, and S7158. Several hydrous inclusions are observed within
236 these single crystals, which formed during quenching and are a common feature in
237 crystals grown from a hydrous melt. Because single crystals of bridgmanite in the
238 present study are larger than 100 μm in dimension, pure and clear regions can be
239 selected for the FTIR measurements.

240 **3.2 Composition**

241 The compositions of the phases in the recovered samples are shown in Tables 2
242 and S1. Single crystals of bridgmanite and coexisting phases in most runs are

243 chemically homogeneous, which is confirmed by element mapping of the recovered
244 samples in Figs. S4–S6. For aluminous bridgmanite, we derived both the OV
245 (MgAlO_{2.5}) and CC (AlAlO₃) components from the equation (Liu et al., 2017):

$$246 \quad \text{Mg}_x\text{Al}_z\text{Si}_y\text{O}_{x+1.5z+2y} = y\text{MgSiO}_3 + (x - y)\text{MgAlO}_{2.5} + \frac{(z-x+y)}{2}\text{AlAlO}_3 \quad (3)$$

247 where $x + y + z = 2$, and x , y , and z are the atomic numbers of Mg, Si, and Al in
248 bridgmanite, respectively. We note that the CC component dominates in most of the
249 single crystals of bridgmanite grown from both stoichiometric and MgO-rich
250 non-stoichiometric hydrous oxide mixtures (runs S7119, IRIS680, and S7139), which
251 reach a maximum of 8 mol% in bridgmanite under 26 GPa and 1900 K in run S7139.
252 In contrast, the OV component only dominates in bridgmanite grown from the
253 MgO-rich non-stoichiometric En₉₀Brm₁₀ glass starting material in run IRIS669. The
254 hydrous melt is MgO-rich in chemical composition. The Mg/Si ratio of the hydrous
255 melt is approximately 2.81 ± 0.01 at 23 GPa and 1900 K (run S7119), and increases to
256 4.03 ± 0.15 (run IRIS669) and 4.30 ± 0.22 (run S7139) at 26 GPa and 1900 K. For (Fe,
257 Al)-bearing bridgmanite in run S7158, the Fe³⁺/ΣFe ratio is $84\% \pm 8\%$. The CC
258 component in the form of FeAlO₃ is derived to be 5 ± 1 mol% and the OV component
259 is 2 ± 1 mol% (Table S1). The calculation method is given in Liu et al. (2020). In run
260 H4851, we found the chemical composition of (Fe, Al) bridgmanite to be relatively
261 heterogenous because of temperature fluctuations owing to unstable heating power,
262 which is also confirmed in the BSE image that shows chemical zoning in the crystals
263 (Fig. 1e). The CC component in the form of FeAlO₃ dominates in bridgmanite in runs
264 S7158 and H4851, whereas the OV component in the form of MgAlO_{2.5} and
265 MgFe_{0.5}Al_{0.5}O_{2.5} plays a negligible role.

266 3.3 FTIR analysis

267 We conducted unpolarized FTIR measurements on clean, pure, and nearly

268 transparent regions of single crystals of bridgmanite of 100–300 μm using a small
269 aperture size (30 μm). We can therefore avoid the interference of inclusions of
270 hydrous melt, hydrous phases, and/or brucite. As shown in Figs. 3–5 and S7–S9, the
271 pure and clean single crystals of both Al- and (Fe, Al)-bearing bridgmanite do not
272 show strong OH-stretching bands at 3000–3600 cm^{-1} , which were observed in earlier
273 studies (Meade et al., 1994; Murakami et al., 2002; Litasov et al., 2003).
274 OH-stretching bands are observed for garnet (3641 cm^{-1}) and stishovite (2664, 2952,
275 3128, and 3327 cm^{-1}) (Fig. 3), which is consistent with previous studies
276 (Bolfan-Casanova et al., 2002; Litasov et al., 2002). Broad bands at 3400–3521 cm^{-1}
277 near the 3641 cm^{-1} garnet and 3327 cm^{-1} stishovite peaks (Fig. 3d) are also observed
278 in the aggregates of garnet/stishovite grains. This suggests that the broad bands at
279 3400–3521 cm^{-1} likely originate from the inclusions of fluids captured within or
280 between grains. In contrast, OH-stretching bands are not observed in the pure single
281 crystals of bridgmanite. In particular, there is almost no change of IR spectra with
282 varying thickness from 200 to 102 μm for the bridgmanite sample from run IRIS669
283 (Fig. 4). Furthermore, light interferences are observed across the bridgmanite platelets
284 in the samples from runs S7139 (Fig. S7), IRIS669 (Fig. 4), IRIS680 (Fig.S8), and
285 H4851 (Fig. S9), which indicates that the water solubility in these bridgmanites is
286 below the detection limit.

287 In contrast, broad and strong OH-stretching bands are clearly observed at
288 frequencies of \sim 3000–3600 cm^{-1} in the IR analysis with an aperture of 45–60 μm on
289 the aggregates of bridgmanite grains (Figs. 3d, 4c, 4f, 5f, S7c, S7d, S8c, S9c) with a
290 sharp peak located at 3690 cm^{-1} associated with brucite. These bands are similar to
291 those reported by Murakami et al. (2002), Litasov et al. (2003), and Bolfan-Casanova
292 et al. (2003). The IR bands at \sim 3350 and 3400 cm^{-1} in Figs. 3 and 4 have been

293 assigned to the OH-stretching bands of superhydrous phase B (Cynn et al., 1996;
294 Bolfan-Casanova et al., 2003), which are observed in the low-temperature regions of
295 the capsule in runs S7119 and IRIS669. Broad and strong IR bands at $\sim 3000\text{--}3600$
296 cm^{-1} from IR spots on the aggregates of bridgmanite grains suggest contributions
297 from hydrous melt or hydrous phases inside the grains or between the grain
298 boundaries, which was also suggested by Bolfan-Casanova et al. (2003). The IR band
299 at 3690 cm^{-1} from brucite is consistently observed on the boundaries of grains in our
300 capsules. This suggests that brucite from the residual melt formed along the grain
301 boundaries during temperature quenching at high pressure.

302 **4. Discussion**

303 The water solubility in a mineral under lower-mantle conditions is conveniently
304 defined as the equilibrium water content of the mineral coexisting with hydrous melt
305 (Keppler and Bolfan-Casanova, 2006). Accordingly, the water solubility in such a
306 mineral equals its maximum water content in a phase assemblage under the given
307 pressure and temperature conditions. In the present study, bridgmanite always coexists
308 with hydrous melt in addition to hydrous phase, garnet, stishovite, or periclase at
309 pressure and temperature conditions of the top of the lower mantle (Table 1, Figs. 1,
310 2). The water solubilities in bridgmanite, garnet, and stishovite in the present study
311 therefore represent their maximum water contents.

312 As shown in Table 1 and Fig. 6, the water solubility in the present Al- and (Al,
313 Fe)-bearing bridgmanite is below 50 ppm wt. H_2O at 24–26 GPa and 1700–1900 K,
314 which is nearly dry under conditions of the top of the lower mantle. At 24 GPa and
315 1900 K (run S7119), aluminous bridgmanite coexists with garnet, stishovite, and

316 hydrous melt. The derived water solubility in bridgmanite in this run is 15 ± 5 ppm wt.
317 H_2O . In contrast, the water solubility in garnet is evaluated to be 545 ± 122 ppm wt.
318 H_2O by integration of the IR band at 3641 cm^{-1} (Fig. 3b), which is slightly lower than
319 the value obtained in MORB (mid-ocean ridge basalt)-garnet ($810\text{--}1440$ ppm wt. H_2O)
320 by electron recoil detection analysis under conditions corresponding to the top of the
321 lower mantle (Panero et al., 2020). If we integrate another IR band at 3502 cm^{-1} in
322 addition to that at 3641 cm^{-1} , the water solubility increases to 1570 ± 34 ppm wt. H_2O .
323 However, this broad IR band mostly originates from hydrous melt, as observed in Fig.
324 3d. The water solubility in aluminous stishovite is 295 ± 55 ppm wt. H_2O , which is
325 close to the value reported by Litasov et al. (2002) under similar pressure and
326 temperature conditions, but lower than that reported by Panero et al. (2003). The
327 derived partition coefficient of water between garnet and bridgmanite is 36 ± 0.4 , and
328 the value between stishovite and bridgmanite is 20 ± 0.4 . These values are close to the
329 result (~ 21) for water partitioning between ringwoodite and bridgmanite by Inoue et
330 al. (2010), but significantly lower than the value (~ 1400) reported by
331 Bolfan-Casanova et al. (2003). Bolfan-Casanova et al. (2000) claimed that akimotoite,
332 which coexists with bridgmanite at the top of the lower mantle, contains ~ 425 ppm wt.
333 H_2O . From these water partitioning experiments, it is thus expected that water will
334 preferentially partition into ringwoodite, garnet, akimotoite, or stishovite rather than
335 bridgmanite at the base of the mantle transition zone or the top of the lower mantle.
336 Subducted slabs dominated by akimotoite, garnet, and stishovite may therefore
337 introduce some amount of water into the top of the lower mantle.

338 At a low temperature of 1700 K at 26 GPa, phase D will form and coexist with
339 aluminous bridgmanite with trace amounts of hydrous melt. Even at this low
340 temperature, bridgmanite is essentially dry. At a higher temperature of 1900 K,
341 aluminous bridgmanite with only coexisting hydrous melt is also dry. Furthermore,
342 (Fe, Al)-bearing bridgmanite coexisting with ferropericlaase and hydrous melt at 26
343 GPa and 1900 K contains a small amount of water (12 ± 2 ppm wt. H₂O), which is
344 almost dry. Our results thereby provide additional experimental evidence for nearly
345 dry bridgmanite at the top of the lower mantle, confirming earlier findings on the very
346 low water solubility in bridgmanite (Bolfan-Casanova et al., 2003).

347 More recently, Fu et al. (2019) reported that (Al, Fe)-bearing bridgmanite
348 synthesized at 24 GPa and 2100 K can contain 1020 ± 70 ppm wt. H₂O based on
349 SIMS measurements (Fig. 6), which is also confirmed by the existence of
350 OH-stretching bands at ~ 3230 and ~ 3460 cm⁻¹ from FTIR measurements. Similar IR
351 bands were previously observed in Litasov et al. (2003) and thought to be caused by
352 hydrous inclusions inside or between grains (Bolfan-Casanova et al., 2003). The
353 possible existence of nano-sized inclusions in their crystals that were difficult to
354 detect using transmitted light, SEM, and transmission electron microscopy cannot be
355 ruled out. Our results indicate that single crystals of bridgmanite smaller than 100 μ m
356 in size easily trap tiny hydrous inclusions, as shown by our FTIR spectra and optical
357 micrographs of such small bridgmanite grains (Figs. 1–6, S2–S9). In our study, single
358 crystals of (Fe, Al)-bearing bridgmanite were grown up to 100–200 μ m, which
359 allowed access to more clean and pure regions for FTIR measurements compared with

360 the study by Fu et al. (2019).

361 The high water solubility reported in earlier studies mostly arises from the
362 integration of the broad and strong IR bands at 3000–3600 cm^{-1} (Murakami et al.,
363 2002; Litasov et al., 2003). Here our measured unpolarized FTIR spectra on the
364 aggregates of small crystals of bridgmanite and their grain boundaries in the
365 low-temperature part of the capsule show similar strong and broad bands as those
366 observed in the aforementioned studies. However, none of these strong and broad IR
367 bands are observed in the pure and clean large-sized single crystals of bridgmanite
368 (Figs. 3–5, S7–S9). This further suggests that the observed IR broad bands are most
369 likely from inclusions of hydrous melt or hydrous phases trapped between the
370 boundaries/cracks or within fine-grained bridgmanite after quenching, which is
371 consistent with the results of Bolfan-Casanova et al. (2003), Panero et al. (2015), and
372 Schmandt et al. (2014). Based on our new results, we conclude that bridgmanite is
373 nearly dry at the top of the lower mantle.

374 Earlier studies claimed that MgO-rich conditions will favor the formation of
375 OV_s in bridgmanite in the presence of trivalent cations, which may provide suitable
376 storage sites to incorporate water into the bridgmanite structure (Navrotsky, 1999;
377 Murakami et al., 2002; Litasov et al., 2003). In this study, we obtained single crystals
378 of OV-dominated bridgmanite (3 ± 1 mol% OV and 1 ± 1 mol% CC) up to 300 μm
379 from MgO-rich $\text{En}_{90}\text{Brm}_{90}$ glass in a hydrous environment (run IRIS669). Several IR
380 spectra on this pure and clean single crystal of OV-dominated bridgmanite suggest
381 that the water solubility is below 50 ppm wt. H_2O (Figs. 4, 6), which is far below its

382 calculated value of ~2 wt.% H₂O by the protonation of OV_s under MgO-saturated
383 synthesis conditions and thus consistent with the result of Bolfan-Casanova et al.
384 (2003). To further clarify whether or not OV_s induce the incorporation of water into
385 bridgmanite, high-pressure and high-temperature experiments must be performed by
386 annealing OV-bearing bridgmanite under hydrous conditions.

387 Bridgmanite is the most abundant mineral (up to 80 vol.%) in a pyrolitic lower
388 mantle (Irifune, 1994). Its water storage capacity is thus of great significance for
389 understanding the dynamics of the lower mantle. Ferropericlase, another major
390 mineral in this region, can contain no more than 50 ppm wt. H₂O (Fig. 6)
391 (Bolfan-Casanova et al. 2002; Litasov, 2010). Even if we consider the case of some
392 amount of water in davemaoite (CaSiO₃ perovskite) (Chen et al., 2020) and hydrous
393 phases such as phase D and phase H in this region (e.g., Ohtani et al., 2004; Nishi et
394 al., 2014), ambient lower-mantle temperatures (Katsura et al., 2010) are too high for
395 the stability of hydrous minerals (Walter et al., 2015). The presence of metallic iron
396 would cause the top of the lower mantle to be more dry because iron would react with
397 hydroxyl in the hydrous and nominally anhydrous minerals (Zhu et al., 2019). We
398 therefore conclude that the majority of the top region of a pyrolitic lower mantle is
399 nearly dry.

400 Consequently, the transport of water-rich nominally anhydrous minerals (e.g.,
401 ringwoodite, garnet) from the bottom of a relatively wet transition zone to the top of a
402 nearly dry pyrolitic lower mantle will cause partial melting (Schmandt et al., 2014).
403 The occurrence of partial melt may reduce the strength of grain boundaries and hence

404 produce seismic low-velocity anomalies below the 660 discontinuity in the lower
405 mantle (e.g., Schmandt et al., 2014; Hier-Majumder et al., 2014; Liu et al., 2018).

406

407 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

408 **Zhaodong Liu:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis,
409 Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Writing–original draft,
410 Writing–review & editing. **Hongzhan Fei:** Formal analysis, Investigation,
411 Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Luyao Chen:** Investigation, Methodology.
412 **Catherine McCammon:** Investigation, Methodology. **Ran Liu:** Investigation,
413 Methodology. **Lin Wang:** Investigation, Methodology. **Fei Wang:** Investigation,
414 Methodology. **Bingbing Liu:** Investigation, Methodology. **Tomoo Katsura:** Funding
415 acquisition, Project administration, Writing–review & editing.

416

417 **Declaration of competing interest**

418 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
419 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

420

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433

434 **Appendix A. Supplementary material**

435 The following is the Supplementary material related to this article.

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567 **Fig.2.** BSE images of run products from various hydrous starting materials. Abbreviations: Gar, garnet;

568 Brg, bridgmanite; Sti, stishovite; Ph D, Phase D; Per, periclase; Fp, ferropericlase; Hym, hydrous melt.

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570 **Fig. 3.** Typical FTIR spectra taken on spots of single crystals of bridgmanite (S-Brg) coexisting with
 571 garnet (Gar), stishovite (Sti), brucite (Bru), superhydrated B (Su B), and hydrous melt (Hym) in run
 572 S7119, where a–d are the measured spots. Blue lines are the fitting curves, while green lines are the
 573 baseline. Red lines are the total fitting curves. Two sharp peaks at ~ 2330 and 2360 cm^{-1} are possibly
 574 from the vibrations of CO_2 or N_2 in the flushed dry air (Rege and Yang, 2001). Inset images are optical
 575 micrographs of the sample and enlarged micrographs of regions a and c in transmitted light.

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583 **Fig. 4.** Optical micrograph obtained under crossed nicols (left) and FTIR spectra on single-crystal (S)
 584 and aggregates of polycrystalline (P) aluminous bridgmanite (Brg) coexisting with brucite (Bru),
 585 superhydrous phase B (SuB), and hydrous melt (Hym) within the capsule in run IRIS669, where a–f
 586 are the measured spots. Spectra of a–c are from the sample with a thickness of 200 μm , while d–f are
 587 from the same sample with a thinner thickness of 102 μm .

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600 **Fig. 5.** Optical micrograph (top left), Mössbauer spectrum (bottom left), and FTIR spectra on
 601 single-crystal (S) and aggregates of polycrystalline (P) (Fe, Al)-bearing bridgmanite (Brg) coexisting
 602 with ferropericlasite, hydrous melt (Hym), and trace amounts of brucite (Bru) in run S7158, where a–e
 603 are the selected spots for FTIR measurements.

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622 **Fig. 6.** Water solubility in bridgmanite (Brg), garnet (Gar), stishovite (Sti), and periclase

623 (Per)/ferropericlase (Fp) synthesized from various hydrous compositions from our study and earlier

624 studies under the pressure and temperature conditions of the top of the lower mantle.

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639 **Table 1** Run number, starting material, pressure (P)-temperature (T) conditions, run products, and
 640 water content in the phases.

Run No.	Starting Comp.	P (K)/Time (hour)	(GPa)/T	Run products	Thickness (μm)	H ₂ O (ppm wt.)	
S7119	En ₉₀ Cor ₁₀ +8.8wt.% oxide mix	H ₂ O	24/1900*/21	Gar+Brg+Sti+Hym	198	Gar:545 (122) Brg: 15 (5) Sti: 295 (55)	
S7139	En ₉₀ Cor ₁₀ +8.8wt.% oxide mix	H ₂ O	26/1900/24	Brg+ Hym	102	–	
IRIS680	En ₉₀ Brm ₁₀ +8.8wt.% oxide mix	H ₂ O	26/1700*/24	Brg+Ph D+ Hym	102	–	
IRIS669	En ₉₀ Brm ₁₀ glass+6 H ₂ O	wt.%	26/1900/30	Brg+Hym+Per+trace Bru.	200	Brg: 17 (9)	
H4851	En ₉₀ FA ₁₀ +10 oxide mix	wt%	H ₂ O	26/1900#/12	Brg+Hym+Fp	74	–
S7158	En ₉₀ FA ₁₀ glass+10 H ₂ O	wt%	26/1900*/24	Brg+Hym+Fp+trace Su B	100	Brg: 12 (2)	

641 *Temperature is evaluated from its relationship with heating power in earlier experiments with the
 642 same cell assembly; # Fluctuation of temperature is caused by unstable heating power. A short dash (–)
 643 represents that signals of water are below the detection limit of FTIR spectroscopy. Abbreviations: Gar,
 644 garnet; Brg, bridgmanite; Ph D: phase D; Su B, superhydrous phase B; Sti, stishovite; Per, periclase; Fp,
 645 ferropericlase; Bru, brucite; Sti, stishovite; Hym, hydrous melt.

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655 **Table 2.** Chemical compositions of run products.

Run No.	Phases	MgO	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	Total	Mg	Al	Si	O	Mg/Si	OV (mol.%)	CC (mol.%)	En (mol.%)
S7119	Brg (n = 15)	39.12(40)	2.06 (16)	57.97 (68)	99.14(84)	0.983(7)	0.041 (3)	0.926 (6)	2.977(8)	1.01 (1)	1 (1)	2 (1)	97 (1)
	Gar (n = 20)	31.84 (44)	18.00 (42)	48.05 (58)	97.89 (58)	0.816 (9)	0.362 (7)	0.822 (9)	2.990 (5)	0.99 (2)			
	Sti (n = 2)	0.02 (1)	1.66 (8)	97.43 (70)	99.11 (62)	0 (0)	0.020 (1)	0.980 (1)	2.000 (0)				
	Hym (n = 10)	40.19 (54)	3.12 (12)	21.62 (48)	64.92 (47)	0.997 (13)	0.031 (1)	0.360 (8)	1.793 (2)	2.81 (1)			
S7139	Brg (n = 22)	37.02 (34)	8.89 (28)	54.87 (59)	100.78 (39)	0.916 (8)	0.174 (6)	0.910 (8)	2.997 (7)	1.01 (2)	1 (1)	8 (1)	91 (1)
	Hym (n = 5)	40.18 (73)	7.43 (49)	13.94 (46)	61.46 (29)	0.997 (18)	0.144 (10)	0.232 (8)	1.677 (13)	4.30 (22)			
IRIS680	Brg (n =16)	37.90 (51)	5.95 (87)	55.99 (54)	99.84 (65)	0.946 (14)	0.117 (17)	0.937 (8)	2.996 (7)	1.01 (2)	1 (1)	5 (1)	94 (1)
	Ph D(n =18)	9.09 (17)	48.20 (36)	27.35 (40)	84.65 (54)	0.226 (4)	0.946 (7)	0.455 (7)	2.554 (17)	0.50 (1)			
IRIS669	Brg (n = 29)	39.55 (42)	2.53 (36)	57.41 (44)	99.47 (65)	0.988 (7)	0.050 (7)	0.962 (6)	2.987 (6)	1.03 (1)	3 (1)	1 (1)	96 (1)
	Hym (n = 5)	44.37 (97)	2.43 (12)	16.43 (68)	63.22 (149)	1.101 (24)	0.048 (2)	0.273 (11)	1.719(42)	4.03 (15)			
	Per (n = 5)	99.03 (74)	0.39 (4)	0.01 (1)	99.43 (76)	0.997 (0)	0.003 (0)		1.002 (0)				

656 Oxide analyses are reported in wt.%. n: number of analysis points. The total cation number is normalized to two. Number in parentheses represents the standard

657 deviation for the last digit(s). Abbreviations: Brg, bridgmanite; Gar, garnet; Sti, stishovite; Per, periclase; Ph D: phase D; Hym, hydrous melt; OV, MgAlO_{2.5}; CC,

658 AlAlO₃; En, MgSiO₃.

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